

Experimental study of damping enhancement in aluminium rods by knurling

A Thesis Submitted
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Degree of
Master of Technology

by

Suparno Bhattacharyya

to the
Department of Mechanical Engineering
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANPUR
INDIA

July, 2014

*To all who have been a positive influence on my life,
especially my parents*

Certificate

It is certified that the work completed in the thesis entitled **Experimental study of damping enhancement in aluminium rods by knurling** by **Suparno Bhattacharyya** has been carried out under my supervision and this work has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

Anindya Chatterjee
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur
Kanpur 208 016, India

July, 2014

Acknowledgments

I am grateful to everyone who has been a part in the completion of this thesis. It would not have been possible without their participation.

First and foremost, I offer my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Anindya Chatterjee, who has supported me throughout my work with his patience and knowledge while allowing me space to work in my own way. I feel all the experience and knowledge that I have acquired throughout the process will be highly beneficial for me as I progress further in my academic career.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Prof. Atanu K. Mohanty of Instrumentation and Applied Physics department, IISc Bangalore. He has offered excellent guidance in theoretical as well as experimental aspects of my project. I am thankful to him for helping me with the analytical estimation of air damping and in the designing and building of various analog filter circuits which were used in my experiments for data processing. It was truly a rewarding experience to get a chance to work with him.

I want to extend my gratitude to all my dear friends, lab mates and seniors for their support. I am especially thankful to Arindam Bhattacharjee, Prasun Jana and Numan Ahmad for their excellent technical advice and help.

I would to also like to thank Mr. Pratik Das (aerospace engineering department), Mr. Anshul Faye (doctoral student under Dr.

Sumit Basu), Mr. Manoj Kr Gautam (assistant of Dr. P. Venkitanarayanan's Laboratory), staff of central workshop IIT Kanpur, and Mr. Satyaprakash (assistant of Prof. Ishan Sharma's Laboratory) for introducing me to various relevant experimental techniques and helping me to procure necessary items for my experimental set-up.

Finally, I want to express my sincere thanks to my family especially to my mother for their unconditional support and love. I would not have been able to make it through my Masters or any of the tough times in my life without them.

Abstract

The present work is motivated by an interest in the damping behaviour of lightly damped metal components. Prior studies have suggested that near surface plastic deformation like shot peening can increase the damping of metallic components. Following up on that idea, we have studied the damping behaviour of slender aluminium rods supported at one of the nodes of the first free-free mode, vibrating in the first mode. Three types of rods were studied. The first one was a plain aluminium rod obtained commercially from the market, the second one was the same rod but with knurling on the surface and the third one, used purely for reference purpose was plain aluminium rod with electrical insulation (viscoelastic) tapes wound on it. Two rods of each type were studied. After the rods were struck, the free vibration response of each rod was measured and recorded. Noise reduction in the measurement was carried out using both analog and digital filters. Ten such measurements were taken for each rod and corresponding to each oscillation the damping co-efficients for free vibration were determined. Results were found to be consistent across ten measurements and two rods within each pair, but the pairs were

found to be significantly different from each other. In particular, the damping in knurled rods was found to be significantly (approximately 60%) higher than plain rods. For reference, this was not as effective as adding visco-elastic tape, which increased the damping by a factor of 2.3. However, as indicated earlier our interest in this work remained in the effect of the knurling on damping behaviour. The possible role of air damping in enhancing the dissipation for knurled rods was investigated analytically and numerically (using FLUENT), and it was concluded that air damping was not a dominant cause for the increase in damping of the knurled rods. It was further concluded that knurling which represents a surface deformation process can have significant effect on the damping property of metals just like shot peening, studied in previous works.

keywords: Dissipation, damping coefficient, hysteresis, dislocation density, knurling

Contents

Certificate	i
Acknowledgment	ii
Abstract	v
Contents	vii
List of Figures	ix
List of Tables	xii
Nomenclature	xiii
1 Introduction	1
2 Experimental study of damping in aluminium rods	5
2.1 List of equipment	5
2.2 Experimental setup	8
2.3 Design philosophy for the experimental set up	10
2.3.1 Initial planning	10
2.3.2 Design of the aluminium rods	11
2.3.3 Support configuration	12
2.3.4 Location of the strain gauge	15
2.3.5 Circuit	15
2.4 Experimental Procedure	18

3	Results	19
3.1	Numerical evaluation of damping	20
3.1.1	Quadratic model of damping	21
3.1.2	Determination of parameters	21
3.1.3	Model without dry friction	25
4	Interpretation of obtained results	33
4.1	Air damping	34
4.1.1	Dissipation through acoustic radiation	34
4.1.2	Viscous dissipation	41
5	Conclusion	51
A	Details of chapter 2	53
A.1	Derivations related to the design of Aluminum rods . .	53
A.2	Location of nodes	57
B	Circuits	58
B.1	Differential Amplifier	58
B.2	Bandpass Filter	59
B.3	Notch Filter	60
B.4	Inverting Amplifier	61
C	Details of chapter 4	63
	References	66

List of Figures

1.1	A typical hysteretic loop associated with material damping (<i>source: W., De Silva Clarence. Vibration Damping, Control, and Design. Boca Raton: Taylor & Francis, 2007.)</i>	2
2.1	Different type of aluminium rods used in the experiment.	7
2.2	The experimental setup. (a) Real-time display of the response, (b) Data acquisition system, (c) Circuit used for amplification and filtering of the measured response, (d) Aluminium rod, (e) Knife edge support, (f) Strain gauge, (g) Horizontal aluminium rod.	9
2.3	Two types of specimens used in the experiment and associated dimensions. On the left is a plain and on the right is a knurled rod (hatch lines represent the knurled portion) - all dimensions are in mm.	11
2.4	Enlarged view of support configuration.	12
2.5	Modal analysis of the finite element model of the rods, in ANSYS (the mesh in the models was generated using SOLID187 elements and the modal analysis was carried out using the Block-Lanczos option).	14

2.6	Circuit used for amplification and noise removal.	16
2.7	Schematic diagram of the circuit.	17
3.1	Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod without surface deformation.	19
3.2	Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod with surface deformation.	20
3.3	Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod with visco-elastic tape.	20
3.4	Figure showing one of the few atypical amplitude vs. time plots observed during high amplitude vibration. Although the large-amplitude behaviour might be complicated, the eventual low-amplitude dynamics was the same.	22
3.5	Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with a non-knurled aluminum rod. The figures on the left side highlights the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrates the corresponding data points and fitted curve.	26
3.6	Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with a knurled aluminum rod. The figures on the left side highlights the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrates the corresponding data points and fitted curve.	27

3.7	Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with an aluminum rod with visco-elastic tape. The figures on the left side highlights the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrates the corresponding data points and fitted curve.	28
3.8	Semilog plot showing different decay rates for different rods.	29
4.1	Two dimensional view of oscillating rigid rod oscillating in air with velocity $\omega U_0 e^{i\omega t}$. $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ are the unit vectors along radial and tangential direction respectively. . . .	35
4.2	Figure showing the domain of integration.	38
4.3	Schematic of infinite plate oscillating in air with velocity v	42
4.4	The solutions of the oscillating plate problem (see C) was used for solving the problem of oscillating cylinder.	43
4.5	Model used for simulation.	46
4.6	Plain circular geometry and the surrounding fluid domain.	48
4.7	Circular geometry with waviness and the surrounding fluid domain.	49
A.1	Schematic of the transverse vibration of the rod	53
A.2	Characteristic equation	55
A.3	Modeshape for first mode of vibration	55

B.1	Circuit diagram of a differential amplifier	58
B.2	Circuit diagram of a bandpass filter	59
B.3	Circuit diagram of a twin-t notch filter	60
B.4	Circuit diagram of an inverting amplifier	61
C.1	Figures showing the real and imaginary parts of Hankel function of second kind	63
C.2	Schematic of infinite plate oscillating in air with veloc- ity v	64

List of Tables

2.1	Obtained from Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (the analysis was performed at Scanning Electron Microscopic facility, corrosion laboratory, department of material science and engineering, IIT Kanpur.)	6
3.1	Table representing value of the coefficients obtained from equation (3.2) in a consolidated manner.	24
3.2	Parameters associated with damping of plain aluminium rods.	30
3.3	Parameters associated with damping of Knurled aluminium rods.	31
3.4	Parameters associated with damping of aluminium rods with visco-elastic tapes.	32
4.1	Table representing results from the previous chapter in a consolidated manner.	34
4.2	Comparison of maximum shear stress values, on the boundary of the oscillating cylinder obtained from equation (4.25), and simulation.	45

Nomenclature

E	Elastic Modulus
$I(x)$	Moment of Inertia
$EI(x)$	Flexural Rigidity
$m(x)$	Mass distribution of the vibrating beam along the axis of the beam
L	Length of the vibrating beam
β	$\sqrt[4]{\frac{\omega^2 m}{EI}}$
$y(x, t)$	Transverse displacement of the beam
c	Velocity of sound in air
p	Pressure
ρ_v	Density of air
ρ_0	Radius of Aluminium rod
$\hat{\rho}$	Unit vector along radial direction
$\hat{\phi}$	Unit vector along tangential direction

Chapter 1

Introduction

Mechanical energy of all vibrating solid dissipates in the form of thermal energy, which eventually causes the vibration to die out. This property of the material is known as damping. Damping is an important characteristic of engineering elements. Unnecessary vibration in these elements may have harmful effects in different situations. Consider metal components which operate near its natural frequency. Without significant amount of damping, a slight disturbance may create resonance condition, causing large amplitude oscillation. Again, consider the case of various automotive parts; unnecessary vibration in these mechanical elements may lead to unwanted noise, structural damage, instability etc. Hence, study of damping characteristics and scope of improving damping properties in engineering materials have been an important area of research for many years. The present thesis also deals with the scope of improving damping property in metals.

There are several types of damping mechanisms associated with mechanical systems. These include (non-exhaustive list) viscous, eddy current, Coulomb, material,

Figure 1.1: A typical hysteretic loop associated with material damping (*source: W., De Silva Clarence. *Vibration Damping, Control, and Design*. Boca Raton: Taylor & Francis, 2007.*)

structural, fluid, thermo-elastic damping etc. Here, we will consider the case of material damping in detail. As evident from [4], material damping occurs mainly due to the energy dissipation associated with microstructural defects like dislocations, grain boundaries and impurities present within the material. During vibration, interaction between these defects especially between dislocations and point defects, along different slip planes, results in internal friction. This eventually leads to dissipation of energy in each stress cycle (refer to [14] for detailed mechanism). The stress–strain relationship for a vibrating element, undergoing this type of damping, involves a hysteresis loop (figure 1.1). The area of this loop quantifies the energy dissipated per stress cycle [13].

Since material damping depends on microstructural defects and their mutual interactions, it can be argued that an increment in the number of defects within the material may actually improve its damping property. Plastic deformations generally produce new dislocations in metals. As a result, there lies a possibility that these new dislocations can in turn affect the material damping of the metals. Following up on this idea we tried to investigate the effect of a near surface plastic deformation process, knurling, on the damping property of aluminium.

Some works relevant to this topic already exist. The scope of improving damping in aluminium-matrix composites through addition of graphite and silicon carbides was studied in [11]. Chung, in his review of materials for vibration damping [2], has given an experimental study on use of metals, polymers and ceramics to reduce vibration in structures and has clearly stated that “damping enhancement in metals mainly involves microstructural design”. However, except for [8], [1] and [12], no other literature seems to be available that can give direct insight into the present problem i.e. the effect of deliberate near-surface plastic deformations on damping in metals. In [1], authors have investigated how cold working affects the correlation between internal friction (within the vibrating continuum) and strain amplitude at low temperatures. The effect of shot peening and sand blasting on damping property of steel has been studied in [8] and [12]. It has been clearly indicated in [8] that damping factor is an important surface characteristics which increases with increase shot peening and compressive residual stress within the material. However, here authors did not provide much insight about the reason for this change. Several studies have been performed which investigate the effect of surface deformation on properties such as fatigue strength [10], fracture toughness [6] etc., of metallic components undergoing cyclic deformation, but little work has been in considering the effect on damping.

In the present work we aimed at estimating the damping property of several aluminium rods with and without surface deformation, through an experimental study. Here, *knurling* was used as the surface deformation process. Our purpose was to check whether any significant change in the damping property of these rods arises owing to such deformations. Analysis of the data, gathered from the experiment revealed that indeed the damping property improved significantly in knurled aluminium rods.

Since the experiment was not carried out in vacuum, there was a possibility of air damping in the vibrating component, that could have significant effect on this improvement. We also considered this fact and estimated the associated air damping. We found that the damping due to air was not the dominant cause behind the increase in damping. From these results we concluded that surface deformation processes like shot peening/knurling can significantly increase damping in metals. We suggest that an increase in the dislocation density during knurling and subsequent increase in energy dissipation during oscillation may be the reason for this change.

Chapter 2

Experimental study of damping in aluminium rods

This chapter describes the experiments conducted with the aluminium rods. During the experiment each rod was struck lightly to induce vibration. The response from each of these rods was recorded using a strain gauge and data acquisition system. The time series for the first mode of vibration was then filtered out from the obtained data and the damping coefficients of each rod were estimated.

We will now discuss in detail the equipment, setup, design philosophy and the procedure of the experiment.

2.1 List of equipment

1. **Aluminium rods:** The aluminium rods used for the experiment were obtained commercially from the market. The chemical composition of one such rod is tabulated below.

Elements	Weight (%)
C	2.34
O	1.21
Mg	0.27
Al	95.36
Si	0.52
Fe	0.31
Total	100

Table 2.1: Obtained from Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (the analysis was performed at Scanning Electron Microscopic facility, corrosion laboratory, department of material science and engineering, IIT Kanpur.)

The experiment was carried out with six aluminium rods for each of which the length and diameter were 834 mm and 11.5 mm respectively. Of these six rods two were plain, two had knurling on a portion of the length, and the remaining two were plain rods with visco-elastic tape wrapped around their surface over a length same as the knurling length. Damping in the third type of rod was studied just to demonstrate the extent of damping that may be achieved with these aluminium rods.

Two holes of 4 mm diameter were drilled on each of the rods at a distance of 187 mm from the ends. The technical aspects behind the design of the rod are discussed in section [2.3](#).

(a) Plain aluminum rod.

(b) Knurled aluminium rod.

(c) Aluminium rod with visco-elastic tape.

Figure 2.1: Different type of aluminium rods used in the experiment.

2. **Strain gauges:** Strain gauges were used to record the deformation of the vibrating rods. The strain gauge specifications were:
 - Resistance: $120\ \Omega$
 - Type: FLA 5-11
 - Gauge Factor(G): 2.11
3. **Data acquisition device:** The Data acquisition systems used were the National instrument *CompactDAQ 4-Slot Ethernet Chassis* and *NI 9215 module*.
4. **Electronic equipment:** Resistances, trimpots, capacitors, bread-boards, IC-741CN, IC-TL084, IC-7805, 9V batteries.
5. **Software:** MATLAB 2013b, LABVIEW 2013.

2.2 Experimental setup

Two holes of 4 mm diameter were drilled on each of the rods before conducting the experiment. The holes were drilled near the two nodes that correspond to the first mode of vibration. During experiment, each rod was suspended from a knife edge support passing through one of these holes. One strain gauge was mounted on each rod, very close to the second nodal point (far away from the one used for supporting; refer to figure 2.3).

Wires coming out of the strain gauges were soldered to a terminal, also mounted on the same aluminium rod. Fine external wires (having very low inertia) were soldered to these terminals and were fed to a *Quarter bridge* circuit. Wires from the strain bridge were connected to another series of circuits for amplification and filtering purpose.

Figure 2.2: The experimental setup. (a) Real-time display of the response, (b) Data acquisition system, (c) Circuit used for amplification and filtering of the measured response, (d) Aluminium rod, (e) Knife edge support, (f) Strain gauge, (g) Horizontal aluminium rod.

The output from this circuit was fed to the data acquisition system, which again was connected to a computer through a USB cable. The responses were recorded in a computer.

A horizontal rod was placed (see figure 2.2) near the second nodal point of the vertical rod and was free to rotate about a vertical axis. The purpose of using this rod was to reduce the rigid body oscillation of the vertical rod occurring immediately after the initial strike. After the impact, the horizontal rod carried away much of the energy associated with the rigid body oscillation of the vertical rod. This eliminated the chance of unwanted motion of the wires connected to strain gauge. Note that the rod was initially struck close to its middle, so that the first mode was excited; and the horizontal rod's impact was at the lower nodal point, so that the first mode response would not be accidentally attenuated.

2.3 Design philosophy for the experimental set up

2.3.1 Initial planning

Our intention in this experiment was to estimate and compare the damping coefficient values of the six aluminium rods corresponding to the first free-free mode of vibration. The reasons for considering first mode were:

- *Low excitation energy requirement.*
- *Simple geometry of the mode-shape.* Due to the simple geometry of the mode shape and convenient location of the nodal points, it was possible to adjust the boundary conditions such that it would facilitate oscillation in the first mode (details about support configuration are discussed later).

2.3.2 Design of the aluminium rods

Figure 2.3: Two types of specimens used in the experiment and associated dimensions. On the left is a plain and on the right is a knurled rod (hatch lines represent the knurled portion) - all dimensions are in mm.

Measurements obtained from electronic instruments often include errors due to line frequency (50 Hz) and its harmonics that act as a source of noise. Thus to

minimize this error the rods were designed such that their first natural frequency lay very close to 75 Hz, sufficiently away from the line frequency and its harmonics. The dimensions of all six rods were identical and calculated using the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory (for details refer to [A](#)). The estimated length and diameter of all the rods were 834 mm and 11.5 mm respectively.

Knurling was done on two of these rods to introduce plastic deformation. The length of the knurling was 400 mm (see figure [2.3](#)).

Apart from analytical solution, a modal analysis of the plain rod was also performed in ANSYS to cross check the value of the natural frequency. The results from the simulation indicated that the first natural frequency was very close to 75 Hz.

2.3.3 Support configuration

As mentioned earlier, for this experiment the first free-free mode of oscillation was used to estimate the damping of the rods. The support condition and the location of the initial impact were chosen so as to ensure excitation of the first mode as well as low external damping of that mode.

Figure 2.4: Enlarged view of support configuration.

Two 4 mm holes were drilled in each rod near the two nodal points of the first mode. The rods were suspended vertically from a knife-edge support passing through one of these holes. The other hole was drilled to maintain the symmetry of the system. It was ensured that the line of contact between the knife-edge and inner surface of the drilled hole merged with the nearby node (figure 2.4 and figure 2.5). Thus minimal movement of the rod near the support was accomplished and the scope of Coulomb damping during vibration was eliminated. It was confirmed through 3D elastodynamics simulation in ANSYS that drilling 4 mm holes did not have any significant effect on the position of the nodes (figure 2.5).

Vibration was induced by striking the rods near the midspan mildly with another small aluminum rod. This was done firstly because the displacement in the first mode is large at the midspan and secondly to prevent excitation of the next higher mode (i.e., the second mode).

(a) Mode shape of the aluminium rod corresponding to the first natural frequency for free-free boundary condition.

(b) The spatial location of the node (marked red) was unchanged in the deformed and undeformed configuration of the rod upon introduction of the 4 mm diameter holes.

Figure 2.5: Modal analysis of the finite element model of the rods, in ANSYS (the mesh in the models was generated using SOLID187 elements and the modal analysis was carried out using the Block–Lanczos option).

2.3.4 Location of the strain gauge

The strain gauge was mounted close to one of the nodes (far away from the one used for supporting; refer to figure 2.3). The strain gauge wires were taken off the rod at the nodal point to ensure that none of the first mode vibrational energy went into those wires.

2.3.5 Circuit

The strain in the rods during vibration was very small, as a result the signal generated from the strain gauge was also very weak. Hence, it was essential to amplify the signal for subsequent analyses. It was also necessary to eliminate the 50 Hz noise (line frequency) before amplification, otherwise the 50 Hz would also get amplified. For this purpose, a circuit (refer to figure 2.6) consisting of a notch filter (for eliminating the 50 Hz), a bandpass filter (with central frequency near the first natural frequency of the rods) and amplifiers (the achieved gain was of the order of 10^4) were built. The amplified and filtered data was then fed to the data acquisition device. Detailed discussion on different parts of the circuit is provided in B.

Figure 2.6: Circuit used for amplification and noise removal.

Figure 2.7: Schematic diagram of the circuit.

2.4 Experimental Procedure

Each rod was given an impulse at the midpoint with a small aluminium rod. The voltage corresponding to amplitude of the vibration as a function of time was obtained from the strain bridge circuit. This signal was then filtered and amplified as mentioned above. The processed signal was then acquired through the data acquisition system and was subsequently transferred to a computer via USB cable. The voltage signal corresponding to the vibration was observed through LABVIEW on the computer. However, due to ease of data processing (done after the experiment) in MATLAB, we recorded the response directly in MATLAB through its inbuilt data acquisition toolbox program. The sampling frequency was 2048 Hz and duration of recording was 150 seconds for all rods.

Ten readings for each rod were taken and thereby a total of 60 time-series data were obtained. We took Fourier transform of each of these time-series and used the bandpass filter (digital) in MATLAB to extract the first mode of vibration. We used a finite impulse response bandpass filter of order 10000 (this order was chosen by trial and error) for this purpose. Coefficients of damping for each aluminium rod were estimated from the processed dataset.

Chapter 3

Results

In this section we provide the details of the numerical estimation of the damping coefficient of the aluminium rods. We then compare the results and conclude that rods with surface deformation exhibit improved damping behaviour.

The following three figures represent samples of raw time-series data acquired from the experiment and also the digitally processed filtered data we used for subsequent analysis. As indicated by the figures, there was some line noise in the measurements, which was successfully removed later by digital filtering. The overall decay envelope was not affected and so the damping estimates are reliable.

Figure 3.1: Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod without surface deformation.

Figure 3.2: Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod with surface deformation.

Figure 3.3: Samples of raw and filtered time-series data for first mode of vibration for an aluminium rod with visco-elastic tape.

3.1 Numerical evaluation of damping

The mathematical models and parameter estimation technique used to determine the damping coefficients in different types of aluminium rods are discussed below.

3.1.1 Quadratic model of damping

We primarily started with the following standard mathematical model of damping to numerically estimate the rate of decay of the oscillation amplitude in different types of aluminum rods:

$$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = -a_1 - a_2A(t) - a_3A(t)^2 \quad (3.1)$$

where

$A(t)$ = averaged oscillation amplitude slowly decaying with time,

a_1 = coefficient of dry friction damping,

a_2 = coefficient of linear or pseudo-linear damping,

a_3 = coefficient of damping due to non-linearities present in the system.

Solving equation (3.1) for t (calculations were carried out in MAPLE) we get

$$t = \begin{cases} \left(\operatorname{arctanh} \left(\frac{2a_3A_0+a_2}{\sqrt{-4a_1a_3+a_2^2}} \right) - \operatorname{arctanh} \left(\frac{2A(t)a_3+a_2}{\sqrt{-4a_1a_3+a_2^2}} \right) \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{-4a_1a_3+a_2^2}} & \text{if } 4a_1a_3 - a_2^2 < 0, \\ 2 \left(\arctan \left(\frac{2a_3A_0+a_2}{\sqrt{4a_1a_3-a_2^2}} \right) - \arctan \left(\frac{2z(t)a_3+a_2}{\sqrt{4a_1a_3-a_2^2}} \right) \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{4a_1a_3-a_2^2}} & \text{if } 4a_1a_3 - a_2^2 > 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

Here A_0 is the initial amplitude of vibration (at time $t = 0$).

3.1.2 Determination of parameters

We estimated the parameters of equation (3.1) from the experimental data in the following manner: For each response obtained during the experiment a portion

Figure 3.4: Figure showing one of the few atypical amplitude vs. time plots observed during high amplitude vibration. Although the large-amplitude behaviour might be complicated, the eventual low-amplitude dynamics was the same.

from the time-series was selected (with amplitude lying between 80% and 20% of the maximum amplitude), and the data points lying on the envelope of that portion were extracted. Afterwards the mathematical model (equation (3.2)) was fitted through these points, and parameters a_1 , a_2 and a_3 were calculated. For this purpose MATLAB's inbuilt optimization algorithm *fminsearch* was used. Further details and relevant figures for this procedure will be presented later. We now address a basic problem with the experimental system.

Due to axisymmetry, the first two natural frequencies of the rods were very close to each other. As a result there was in principle a chance of sideways rocking oscillation resulting in some rattling motion near the knife edge support as well as other non-linear interaction between these two modes. A signature of this was observed in a few data sets where there was an initial decay rate that was non-exponential, followed by an eventually established slower exponential decay rate. Figure 3.4 shows one such time-series. However, because of nearly linear behaviour of the system at lower amplitude, the rate of decay could be approximated well using equation (3.2). We always evaluated the rate of decay for that portion of the

time series where the decay was nearly exponential (e.g the portion marked in red in figure 3.4). But as mentioned earlier, there were only a few such cases; most of the other available data sets were quite consistent and did not show such strongly non exponential behaviour.

After estimating the parameters from equation (3.2) for different cases, we found that in each case the coefficient of dry friction damping was very small (refer to table 3.1). Also the strain associated with the vibration was quite small, of the order of 10^{-5} m, as a result we eventually neglected this term, and re-evaluated the parameters using a second mathematical model.

Type	Coefficient of dry friction damping (mean), a_1	Standard deviation	Coefficient of linear damping (mean), a_2	Standard deviation	Coefficient of quadratic term (mean), a_3	Standard deviation
Plain rod	9.4241×10^{-5}	1.3351×10^{-4}	0.0379	0.0022	0.0122	0.0066
Knurled rod	9.6259×10^{-5}	2.0315×10^{-4}	0.0618	0.0035	0.0236	0.0084
Rod with visco-elastic tape	1.4143×10^{-4}	1.9368×10^{-4}	0.0857	0.0038	0.0506	0.0052

Table 3.1: Table representing value of the coefficients obtained from equation (3.2) in a consolidated manner.

3.1.3 Model without dry friction

As found above, dry friction coefficient seems negligible. A model without dry friction is analytically more convenient. We consider such a model in this section.

In this model along with neglecting the dry friction the power of the quadratic term of equation (3.2) was changed from 2 to a variable m to compensate for the neglected term and at the same time to check whether changing m results in a better fit or not.

The new equation and its solution are given below:

$$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = -a_2A(t) - a_3A(t)^m. \quad (3.3)$$

The solution of equation (3.3) is the following:

$$A(t) = \left(\frac{-a_3 + e^{ta_2(m-1)}A_0^{-m+1}a_2 + e^{ta_2(m-1)}a_3}{a_2} \right)^{-(m-1)^{-1}}. \quad (3.4)$$

The symbols have the same meaning as before. Using this model we again estimated the parameter values from our experimental data (the method of estimation remains the same). We considered both $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ during the calculation. We got a slightly better fit with $m = 3$ (about 1.3 % lower error) and adopted $m = 3$. For completeness, some graphs showing the data points and the fitted curves are given below. The fitted parameter values are given in tables 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4.

Figure 3.5: Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with a non-knurled aluminum rod. The figures on the left side highlight the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrate the corresponding data points and fitted curve.

Figure 3.6: Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with a knurled aluminum rod. The figures on the left side highlight the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrate the corresponding data points and fitted curve.

Figure 3.7: Three sets of figures corresponding to three experimental runs with an aluminum rod with visco-elastic tape. The figures on the left side highlight the portion of the response used to estimate the parameters and figures on the right hand side demonstrate the corresponding data points and fitted curve.

In the following figure, we show a rough comparison of the decay rate for three different types of rods. The plots are in semi-log scale and correspond to two experimental runs of each type of rods. This figure clearly indicates that though not as much as the visco-elastic tape, knurling significantly improved damping property of aluminium rods.

Figure 3.8: Semilog plot showing different decay rates for different rods.

	RUN	Coefficient of linear damping (a_2)	Coefficient of cubic term (a_3)
ALUMINUM ROD WITHOUT KNURLING -I	1	0.0344	0.0297
	2	0.0385	0.0191
	3	0.0397	0.0699
	4	0.0357	0.0602
	5	0.0358	0.0369
	6	0.0411	0.0051
	7	0.0371	0.0660
	8	0.0410	0.0000
	9	0.0388	0.1161
	10	0.0391	0.0091
ALUMINUM ROD WITHOUT KNURLING-II	1	0.0413	0.0057
	2	0.0411	0.0525
	3	0.0400	0.0407
	4	0.0415	0.0300
	5	0.0397	0.0088
	6	0.0410	0.0318
	7	0.0410	0.0000
	8	0.0416	0.0000
	9	0.0408	0.0073
	10	0.0408	0.0000

Table 3.2: Parameters associated with damping of plain aluminium rods.

	RUN	Coefficient of linear damping (a_2)	Coefficient of cubic term (a_3)
KNURLED ALUMINUM ROD -I	1	0.0633	0.5526
	2	0.0697	0.0494
	3	0.0699	0.1362
	4	0.0641	1.3068
	5	0.0624	0.3526
	6	0.0610	0.5921
	7	0.0609	0.3743
	8	0.0651	0.0485
	9	0.0618	0.0386
	10	0.0600	1.2910
KNURLED ALUMINUM ROD -II	1	0.0640	0.0341
	2	0.0636	0.0346
	3	0.0651	0.0276
	4	0.0650	0.0000
	5	0.0657	0.0238
	6	0.0651	0.0000
	7	0.0655	0.0237
	8	0.0642	0.0221
	9	0.0629	0.0336
	10	0.0656	0.0244

Table 3.3: Parameters associated with damping of Knurled aluminium rods.

	RUN	Coefficient of linear damping (a_2)	Coefficient of cubic term (a_3)
ALUMINIUM ROD WITH VISCO-ELASTIC TAPE-I	1	0.0915	0.0000
	2	0.1060	0.0021
	3	0.0934	0.1492
	4	0.1048	0.1462
	5	0.1002	0.0743
	6	0.1027	0.0472
	7	0.0975	0.0167
	8	0.0865	0.1034
	9	0.0885	0.0635
	10	0.0906	0.0000
ALUMINIUM ROD WITH VISCO-ELASTIC TAPE-II	1	0.0831	0.1760
	2	0.0864	0.0000
	3	0.0875	0.0000
	4	0.0843	0.1251
	5	0.0869	0.0000
	6	0.0851	0.0000
	7	0.0877	0.0000
	8	0.0865	0.0000
	9	0.0946	0.0314
	10	0.1120	0.0000

Table 3.4: Parameters associated with damping of aluminium rods with visco-elastic tapes.

Chapter 4

Interpretation of obtained results

As evident from the previous chapter or the consolidated results given in table 4.1, the value of the linear damping coefficient of the knurled aluminium rods is significantly higher than that of the plain ones. The coefficient of the cubic term shows a little erratic behaviour and lacks consistency. Hence the exact significance of this term is not clear at this point. However, the cubic term becomes negligible at smaller amplitudes, and so our interest lies in the behaviour of exponential decay and the coefficient of exponential decay is found to be consistent across ten measurements and across similar type of rods. If we compare the average value of the coefficient for both type of rods we see that for knurled rods it is almost 1.6 times that of plain rods. Since the experiment was not carried out in vacuum, it was considered that apart from internal damping, air damping may also have a role in the increase of damping. To understand things clearly, we estimated the air damping in both type of rods, analytically as well as through simulation, and found that the effect of air damping was not dominant. Thus, it was concluded that the increment of damping in the knurled rods can be attributed primarily to an increase of internal dissipation in the rod.

Type	Coefficient of linear damping (mean)	Standard deviation	Coefficient of cubic term (mean)	Standard deviation
Plain rod-I	0.0381	0.0023	0.0412	0.0366
Plain rod-II	0.0409	6.1×10^{-4}	0.0177	0.0193
Knurled rod-I	0.0646	9.25×10^{-4}	0.0222	0.0134
Knurled rod-II	0.0638	0.0035	0.4742	0.4797
Rod with visco-elastic tape-I	0.0962	0.007	0.0603	0.0578
Rod with visco-elastic tape-II	0.0894	0.0085	0.0332	0.0637

Table 4.1: Table representing results from the previous chapter in a consolidated manner.

4.1 Air damping

To estimate the air damping for small oscillations we assumed linear fluid mechanics for the air. Within this linearized response of the air there is a part which is acoustic, due to compressibility of the air, and a part which is viscous mostly due to viscous dissipation in approximately incompressible air. In the following sections we discuss the effect of both phenomena in detail.

4.1.1 Dissipation through acoustic radiation

Here, we first determined the rate of dissipation of energy due to acoustic radiation from an infinitely long rigid cylinder oscillating in air. We first found a two dimensional solution for this problem. From the knowledge of the first mode shape of the oscillating rod and this two dimensional solution used on a per unit length basis, the dissipation rate for the actual rod was estimated. It was then compared with the net dissipation observed experimentally, and the contribution

of the acoustic effect was found to be negligible. This is not surprising, because the diameter of the rod is about 11.5 mm, while the vibration frequency of 75 Hz corresponds to a wavelength of about 5 m in air (i.e. much larger). Qualitatively, too, the sound of the vibrating rod could only be heard (dimly) when the ear was taken to within a few centimeters from the rod.

Pressure field

Figure 4.1: Two dimensional view of oscillating rigid rod oscillating in air with velocity $\omega U_0 e^{i\omega t}$. $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ are the unit vectors along radial and tangential direction respectively.

In figure 4.1, we show a two dimensional view of a rigid cylinder oscillating in air with a frequency ω . We assume the displacement vector of the oscillating cylinder is of the following form:

$$\vec{u} = U_0 e^{i\omega t} \quad (4.1)$$

where

$U_0 =$ Maximum displacement,

$t =$ time.

Initially we intend to find out the equation of the pressure field (p) around the cylinder due to the oscillation. The governing equations are the following [5]:

$$\nabla^2 p - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad (4.2)$$

$$\frac{\nabla p}{\rho_v} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial t}. \quad (4.3)$$

where the v-subscript on rho is to denote density as opposed to radial direction as in figure 4.1. Let $p = p(\rho, \phi)e^{i\omega t}$. Substituting p in (4.2) we obtain:

$$\nabla^2 p + k^2 p = 0. \quad (\text{where } k = \omega/c) \quad (4.4)$$

The solution of the Helmholtz wave equation (4.4) has the following form in polar coordinates (for wave travelling outwards):

$$p = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} H_m^{(2)}(k\rho)(C_m \cos(m\phi) + B_m \sin(m\phi)), \quad m \in I \quad (4.5)$$

where C_m and B_m are constants, and $H_m^{(2)}$ is the Hankel function of second kind (C). $H_m^{(2)}(x) = J_m(x) - iY_m(x)$ where $J_m(x)$ is Bessel function of first kind, and $Y_m(x)$ is the Bessel function of second kind.

Now let us consider the velocity of the cylinder. On its boundary, the displacement (\vec{u}) and velocity (\vec{V}), in polar coordinates, can be written as:

$$\vec{u} = (U_0 \cos(\phi)\hat{\rho} - U_0 \sin(\phi)\hat{\phi})e^{i\omega t}, \quad (4.6)$$

$$\vec{V} = i\omega(U_0 \cos(\phi)\hat{\rho} - U_0 \sin(\phi)\hat{\phi})e^{i\omega t}. \quad (4.7)$$

It can be seen from figure 4.1 that the oscillating cylinder has velocity components along radial and tangential direction, on each point of the boundary. Since the tangential component has no acoustic effect, only the radial component has been considered for subsequent calculation. Now, as the radial component has dependence only on $\cos(\phi)$ the expression of the pressure field (equation (4.5)) can be reduced to:

$$p = H_1^{(2)}(k\rho)C_1 \cos(\phi). \quad (4.8)$$

Velocity field

The velocity field of the air surrounding the oscillatory cylinder can also be written in the following form:

$$\vec{v} = v(\rho, \phi)e^{i\omega t}. \quad (4.9)$$

Substituting \vec{v} and p from equations (4.9) and (4.8) respectively in equation (4.3) we get:

$$v(\rho, \phi) = \frac{iC_1}{\omega \rho_v} \left(kH_1^{(2)}(k\rho) \cos(\phi) \hat{\rho} - \frac{H_1^{(2)}(k\rho) \sin(\phi)}{\rho} \hat{\phi} \right). \quad (4.10)$$

where

$$H_1^{(2)}(x) = \frac{d}{dx} H_1^{(2)}(x) = \frac{d}{dx} (J_1(x) - iY_1(x)) = J_1'(x) - iY_1'(x)$$

The rate of energy dissipation

Figure 4.2: Figure showing the domain of integration.

Adopting the phasor approach to estimate the rate of energy dissipation per unit length we can write

$$q_{acoustic} = \frac{1}{2} \oint_{-\pi}^{\pi} \Re(p(\rho, \phi)(\hat{\rho} \cdot \bar{v}(\rho, \phi))) \rho d\phi \quad (4.11)$$

where

$q_{acoustic}$ = Energy dissipation per unit length per unit time,

$p(\rho, \phi)$ = Amplitude of the time varying pressure field,

$\bar{v}(\rho, \phi)$ = Complex conjugate of the amplitude of the velocity field.

Equation (4.11) represents the energy dissipated from the oscillating cylinder per unit time per unit length through any closed circular domain lying at a distance ρ

($\rho >$ radius of the cylinder) from the center of the oscillating cylinder (refer to figure 4.2). Here also the *radial component* of the velocity field represented as $\hat{\rho} \cdot \bar{v}(\rho, \phi)$ in equation (4.11) was considered for the analysis.

Substituting the values of pressure and velocity from equations (4.8) and (4.10) respectively in equation (4.11), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} q_{acoustic} &= \oint_{-\pi}^{\pi} \Re \left(\frac{kC_1\bar{C}_1 \cos^2(\Phi)(J_1(k\rho) - iY_1(k\rho))(Y_1'(k\rho) - iJ_1'(k\rho))}{2\omega\rho_v} \right) \rho d\phi \\ &= \oint_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{k|C_1|^2 \cos^2(\Phi)(Y_1'(k\rho)J_1(k\rho) - J_1'(k\rho)Y_1(k\rho))}{2\omega\rho_v} \rho d\phi \end{aligned}$$

But $(Y_1'(k\rho)J_1(k\rho) - J_1'(k\rho)Y_1(k\rho)) = \frac{2}{\pi k\rho}$ therefore

$$\begin{aligned} q_{acoustic} &= \oint_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{k|C_1|^2 \cos^2(\Phi) \left(\frac{2}{\pi k\rho}\right)}{2\omega\rho_v} \rho d\phi \\ &= \frac{|C_1|^2}{\omega\rho_v} \end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

To determine C_1 we impose the velocity boundary condition. On the boundary of the oscillating cylinder the velocity field of air and cylinder velocity are the same. From equations (4.7) and (4.10) equating the radial component of the velocities at $\rho = \rho_0$ (say) we get:

$$U_0 \cos(\phi) i\omega = \frac{iC_1}{\omega\rho_v} k H_1^{(2)'}(k\rho) \cos(\phi) \tag{4.13}$$

From the above equation we obtain

$$C_1 = \frac{U_0 \omega^2 \rho_v}{k H_1^{(2)'}(k\rho_0)}. \tag{4.14}$$

putting $\rho_v = 1.1644 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\omega = 471 \text{ rad/sec}$, $k = 1.3491 \text{ rad/m}$, and $\rho_0 = 0.00575 \text{ m}$ in equations (4.14) and (4.12) we get:

$$q_{acoustic} = -0.596U_0^2. \quad (4.15)$$

Now for the actual rod the value of U_0 varies with the length of the rod. This variation is dependent on the shape function of the mode ($\Phi(x)$) in which the rod vibrates. We can write,

$$U_0(x) = U_0\Phi(x). \quad (4.16)$$

and,

$$q_{acoustic}(x) = -0.596U_0^2\Phi^2(x). \quad (4.17)$$

The losses from the above expression can be integrated over the length of the rod, to get an estimate of the net dissipation. Thus:

$$Q_{acoustic} = -0.596U_0^2 \int_0^L \Phi(x)^2 dx. \quad (4.18)$$

where $U_0\phi(x)$ is the shape function corresponding to the first mode of vibration with maximum amplitude U_0 . $Q_{acoustic}$ is the energy lost per unit time from the aluminum rod in air during oscillation. Again, the rate of change in the *kinetic energy* of the oscillating rod may be written as:

$$\dot{E} = \frac{\omega^2 m U_0 \dot{U}_0}{L} \int_0^L \Phi(x)^2 dx. \quad (4.19)$$

It should be noted that U_0 is not a constant quantity, and decays slowly with time which allows us to speak of its slow average rate of change. Equating equations

(4.18), and (4.19) we obtain:

$$\dot{U}_0 = \frac{-0.596U_0L}{m\omega^2}. \quad (4.20)$$

Substituting $m/L = 0.24 \text{ kg/m}$, and $\omega = 471 \text{ rad/sec}$ we get:

$$\dot{U}_0 = -9.5865 \times 10^{-6}U_0. \quad (4.21)$$

Comparing the equations (4.21) and (3.3), and the tabulated parameter values we see that the rate of amplitude decay in equation (4.21) is much lower than that obtained experimentally. Hence we conclude that the energy dissipation through acoustic radiation in the surrounding air has negligible contribution in damping of the aluminium rods.

4.1.2 Viscous dissipation

To estimate the viscous dissipation due to oscillating cylinder we solved for the motion of the fluid, and treated the velocity condition as given on the boundary of the rod, but unlike the analysis of the acoustic part where only the radial component of the velocity was considered, the viscous effect was determined by considering the tangential velocity component of the oscillating cylinder.

Now this problem itself was again solved using a further approximation of an infinite plate also oscillating with frequency ω while in contact with a viscous fluid. For this case we found the characteristic length, i.e. the depth to which the disturbance propagated into the fluid, was approximately 0.257 mm (refer to C for detailed analysis). Since this was rather small compared to the diameter of the rod (roughly 2 percent of 11.5 mm) it was concluded that an order of magnitude estimation of the damping could be obtained by using the planar solution, and integrating it over the perimeter of the cylinder.

Figure 4.3: Schematic of infinite plate oscillating in air with velocity v .

In this case the velocity of the fluid surrounding the oscillating plate can be written as:

$$u(y, t) = v_0 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\nu}} \frac{1+i}{\sqrt{2}} y + i\omega t} \quad (4.22)$$

The notations should not be confused with that of the previous section specifically, there should be no confusion with equations (4.1) and (4.9). Here:

u = velocity of the medium,

ν = kinematic viscosity of the medium,

$v = v_0 e^{i\omega t}$, velocity of the plate.

Now, for the actual problem (refer to figure 4.1) $v_0 = \omega U_0 \sin(\phi)$, since for viscous dissipation only the tangential velocity component of the cylinder was considered.

Figure 4.4: The solutions of the oscillating plate problem (see C) was used for solving the problem of oscillating cylinder.

The rate of energy dissipation was obtained by calculating the dissipation rate *at the boundary* of the cylinder due to the engendered shear force (τ) inside the medium. The shear stress, and the fluid velocity at the boundary was obtained by substituting $y = 0$ in equation (4.22), and equation (4.25). We followed similar methodology used in the previous section. The following equation was used to estimate the dissipation per unit length

$$q_{viscous} = \frac{1}{2} \oint_{-\pi}^{\pi} \Re(\tau_{amplitude}(0, \phi, t) \bar{u}_{amplitude}(0, \phi, t)) \rho_0 d\phi \quad (4.23)$$

where \bar{u} denotes the complex conjugate of u . Now, from equation (4.22)

$$u(0, \phi, t) = \omega U_o \sin(\phi) e^{i\omega t} \quad (4.24)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(y, \phi, t) &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \\ &= \mu \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (U_o \omega \sin(\phi) e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\nu}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (1+i)y + i\omega t}) \\ &= \mu \omega U_o \sin(\phi) \left(-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\nu}} \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (1+i) e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\nu}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (1+i)y + i\omega t} . \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\tau(0, \phi, t) = \mu\omega U_0 \sin(\phi) \left(-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\nu}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+i)\right) e^{i\omega t} \quad (4.25)$$

From equation (4.23), equation (4.24), and equation (4.25) the rate of energy dissipation per unit length can be written as:

$$q_{viscous} = -U_0^2 \omega^2 \rho_0 \pi \sqrt{\frac{\mu\omega\rho_v}{8}}. \quad (4.26)$$

Putting $\rho_v = 1.1644 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\omega = 471 \text{ rad/sec}$, $k = 1.3491 \text{ rad/m}$, and $\mu = 1.983 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Kg/ms}$ in equation (4.26) we get:

$$q_{viscous} = -6.6620 \times 10^{-4} U_0^2 \omega^2. \quad (4.27)$$

Now following equation (4.16), and equation (4.17) for this case also we can write,

$$q_{viscous}(x) = -6.6620 \times 10^{-4} U_0^2(x) \omega^2. \quad (4.28)$$

$U_0(x)$ is same as before.

Determining the decay rate

The rate of energy dissipation of the entire rod was given by:

$$Q_{viscous} = \int_0^L q_{viscous}(x) dx. \quad (4.29)$$

or,

$$Q_{viscous} = -6.6620 \times 10^{-4} U_0^2 \omega^2 \int_0^L \Phi^2(x) dx. \quad (4.30)$$

$Q_{viscous}$ is the energy lost due to viscous effect per unit time from the aluminum rod in air during vibration. Again considering the rate of change in the *kinetic energy*

of the oscillating rod from equation (4.19), and comparing it with equation (4.30) we obtain:

$$\dot{U}_0 = \frac{-6.6620 \times 10^{-4} U_0 L}{m}. \quad (4.31)$$

Substituting $m/L = 0.24$ kg/m we get:

$$\dot{U}_0 = -0.0023 U_0. \quad (4.32)$$

This shows that the linear damping coefficient (coefficient of U_0) is almost 17 times smaller than the value obtained from experimental results. Since an approximation has been made in estimating this problem, a FLUENT simulation was also done for the validation of the results. The details of the simulation is given in the following section.

FLUENT Simulations

Here we have simulated the oscillation of the 2-D model of the cylinder, in FLUENT. The model was treated as a bounded circular region having radius same as the cylinder with fluid flowing, in a square domain, outside this region. For simulating oscillation of the cylinder, periodic velocity boundary condition (for $\omega = 75$ Hz, and maximum displacement = 0.001 m) was imposed. On the outer boundaries, outlet pressure was set to zero. From data obtained through simulation we then compared the maximum shear stress value induced at the boundary of the circular region, and compared it with our theoretical results.

	SIMULATION	THEORETICAL
τ_{max}	0.021 N/m ²	0.035 N/m ²

Table 4.2: Comparison of maximum shear stress values, on the boundary of the oscillating cylinder obtained from equation (4.25), and simulation.

From the table it can be seen that the value of the shear force developed at the boundary was overestimated in the theoretical model. Since the dissipation rate is directly proportional to the shear force, it appears that the actual dissipation rate is even smaller than our estimate. Hence, we can conclude that the relative contribution of air damping during vibration was not dominant.

Figure 4.5: Model used for simulation.

A final point is that knurling roughens the surface of the rod. This could in principle increase the dissipation in air. How much would the air dissipation have to increase, so that the net increase in overall dissipation could be entirely accounted for in this way? Note that here we are not hoping to precisely quantify the exact amount of increase in internal damping. Our goal is merely to say whether or not a significant amount of increase in internal damping has occurred due to knurling.

Now, as evident from our theoretical estimate, the coefficient of damping in air is about 17 times smaller (referring to the simulation results we can say it may be even smaller!) than the overall observed dissipation rate in the plain rods. For example if the original damping in the plain rods is taken to be 100, then damping in air is about 6 but due to knurling the damping of the plain rods now has increased to 160 (as evident from the experimental data, due to knurling the linear damping coefficient increased by a factor of 1.6). Hence, if we consider air damping to be predominant, then it has to increase from 6 to 66 i.e. by a factor of about 10 to account for this change.

A detailed solution of this oscillating problem is difficult. Hence, a simplified FLUENT simulation was performed for this purpose. Two dimensional geometrical models of both smooth and wavy surfaces (the latter to represent the effect of knurling) were used in the simulation. Here, unlike the previous simulation, the circular geometries were kept fixed inside air which was flowing along x-direction. The inlet velocity of the air was kept constant and it was equal 0.1 m/sec. From pressure and velocity distributions at the inlet, obtained from the steady state solution, the total energy (per unit length) going inside the fluid domain was calculated for both type of geometries (i.e. with and without waviness). A high value of this quantity signifies high energy requirement at the inlet which means the system is dissipating more energy.

We calculated this dissipation in fluid domains with different dimensions to check whether the dissipation value for each type of geometry converges or not. In the following figures two FLUENT simulation models of the circular geometry, with and without waviness, are shown. The dissipation values in different cases are tabulated at the end of this section. The size of the fluid domain depicted here is $30d \times 30d$. (where d is the diameter of the circle)

Figure 4.6: Plain circular geometry and the surrounding fluid domain.

Contours of Static Pressure (pascal)

Jul 11, 2014
ANSYS Fluent 14.5 (2d, dp, pbns, lam)

Contours of Static Pressure (pascal)

Jul 11, 2014
ANSYS Fluent 14.5 (2d, dp, pbns, lam)

Figure 4.7: Circular geometry with waviness and the surrounding fluid domain.

The results we obtained from the simulations are tabulated in the following table:

Dimension of the fluid domain	Energy dissipation rate per unit length for plain geometry $\times 10^{-5}$ (W/m)	Energy dissipation rate per unit length for knurled geometry $\times 10^{-5}$ (W/m)
$30d \times 30d$	1.2974	1.5211
$40d \times 40d$	1.4022	1.4131

From the table it can be seen that the dissipation values are not very different. We do not aim here to establish precise relationships, but rather to point out that the dissipations are certainly not increased by an order of magnitude by waviness on the surface of the rod. Of course, this is a simple simulation, wherein there is steady flow past a fixed rod; but it seems reasonable to conclude that even for an oscillating rod, the increase in air damping due to knurling is **not** increased by an order of magnitude. We therefore conclude that the significant increase in damping observed for the knurled rods is most probably due to changes in the internal dissipation in the rods, in turn brought about by the extensive near-surface deformation due to knurling, and similar to previously observed damping increases brought about by shot peening or sand blasting.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

Our aim in this work was to understand the effect of surface deformation on damping property of metallic components. For that, we studied the effect of knurling, a commonly employed surface deformation process, on the damping of aluminium.

We experimentally observed the free oscillation of aluminium rods with and without surface deformation and studied their damping property. The damping coefficients for both type of rods were determined and compared. We obtained consistent results and found that damping coefficient values for knurled rods were significantly higher than that of plain aluminium rods. It was then analyzed whether the higher damping in knurled rod was due to air. We developed a novel analytical study and FLUENT simulations to estimate the air damping in both type of rods. It was found that the air did not have dominant effect on damping of the rods. As a result, it was concluded that the improved damping was due to increased internal damping within the material.

In this work we have not directly analyzed how surface deformations like knurling affects the internal damping, but developed some insights from the available literature. Knurling being a plastic deformation process can generate new dislocations

and thereby increase the dislocation density within metals [3]. During vibration the random or semi-random movement of these dislocations can increase the amount of energy dissipation within the vibrating continuum.

However, our main contribution lies in the direct experimental demonstration of a surface machining process like knurling as a plausible method of improving damping in metallic components.

Appendix A

Details of chapter 2

A.1 Derivations related to the design of Aluminum rods

Figure A.1: Schematic of the transverse vibration of the rod

We here present the method of finding natural frequency and mode shapes for the rod following L. Meirovitch [9]. The equation of motion for transverse vibration of the rod can be written as:

$$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left[EI(x) \frac{\partial^2 y(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right] = m(x) \frac{\partial^2 y(x,t)}{\partial t^2}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

For free-free oscillation of the rods the following boundary conditions are satisfied:

$$EI(x)\frac{\partial^2 y(0, t)}{\partial x^2} = 0, EI(x)\frac{\partial^2 y(L, t)}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$EI(x)\frac{\partial^3 y(0, t)}{\partial x^3} = 0, EI(x)\frac{\partial^3 y(L, t)}{\partial x^3} = 0. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

For this case

$$E, I, m \text{ are constant}$$

To solve (A.1) let $y(x, t) = Y(x)y(t)$ (method of separation of variable).

This will yield the following decoupled ODEs

$$\frac{d^4 Y(x)}{dx^4} - \beta^4 Y(x) = 0, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\frac{d^2 y(t)}{dt^2} + \omega^2 y(t) = 0. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Solving (A.4) with boundary conditions (A.2) and (A.3) we get the following equations:

$$Y(x) = \frac{1}{2}(-0.9825 \sin(\beta x) - 0.9825 \sinh(\beta x) + \cos(\beta x) + \cosh(\beta x)), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

(Here, we have considered the maximum tip displacement of the rod (at $x = 0$) to be unity.)

and

$$\cos(\beta L) \cosh(\beta L) = 1. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Equation (A.7) is known as characteristic equation. Solution for this transcendental equation was obtained graphically. The solution which corresponds to the first

natural frequency, can be written as:

$$\beta L = 4.73 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where

$$\beta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{\omega^2 m}{EI}}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Figure A.2: Characteristic equation

Figure A.3: Modeshape for first mode of vibration

Considering $\omega = 471.2389$ rad/sec (75 Hz) , $E = 70$ GPa, $m = 0.28$ kg/m and $I = 8.5854 \times 10^{-10}$ m⁴, from (A.8) & (A.9) the length (L) of the rod was calculated to be 834 mm.

A.2 Location of nodes

Nodes are stationary points on the beam vibrating in a particular mode. For the first mode, solving $Y(x) = 0$ (refer to equation (A.6)) for x we obtain:

$$x = 0.187 \text{ and } 0.647 \text{ for } x \in (0, 0.834) \text{ (since length of the rod is } 0.834 \text{ m).}$$

These two solutions represent the location of the two nodes corresponding to the first mode, from one end of the rods.

Appendix B

Circuits

B.1 Differential Amplifier

Figure B.1: Circuit diagram of a differential amplifier

Differential amplifiers are used to amplify difference between two voltage signal without amplifying the particular voltages. It was used to amplify the voltage signal coming from the strain bridge circuit during vibration. The gain in voltage signal due to this circuit was:

$$\text{Gain (G)} = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = -\frac{R_2}{R_1}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

It can be seen from figure 2.7 that for the circuit used in the experiment the $\text{Gain}(G) = \frac{150}{1.5} = 100$.

B.2 Bandpass Filter

Figure B.2: Circuit diagram of a bandpass filter

Bandpass filters are used to filter out signals corresponding to a specific band of frequencies. In this case we designed the bandpass filter in such a way that the voltage signals with frequencies much lower or higher than the first natural frequency of the aluminium rod (471 rad/sec), were eliminated. The transfer function for the circuit shown in figure B.2 can be written as:

$$H(s) = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = -\frac{H_0 \beta s}{s^2 + \gamma s + \omega_0^2}$$

where

$H_0 = -\frac{R_3}{2R_1}$ is the maximum gain corresponding to the central frequency,

$\omega_0 = \frac{\sqrt{R_1 + R_2}}{C\sqrt{R_1 R_2 R_3}}$, is the central frequency. Signals having frequencies near this central frequency pass through the bandpass filter,

$\gamma = \frac{2}{CR_3}$ represents the passband bandwidth, the difference between the upper and lower cutoff frequencies of the bandpass filter.

For our case (refer to figure 2.7) $H_0 = 14.17$, $\omega_0 = 442.81$ rad/sec, $\beta = 117.65$.

B.3 Notch Filter

Figure B.3: Circuit diagram of a twin-t notch filter

Notch filters are used to attenuate signals with a particular frequency. This filter was used to eliminate the 50 Hz noise (coming from the electrical supply lines) from our measurement data. The transfer function for the circuit shown in figure

B.3 can be written as:

$$H(s) = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = 2R_1 + sC_1R_1^2 + \frac{2}{sC_2} + \frac{1}{sC_2^2R_2}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Now the magnitude of the transfer function becomes zero corresponding to the frequency, to be eliminated. From this condition we obtain $R_1 = R$, $R_2 = \frac{R}{2}$, $C_2 = C$, $C_1 = 2C$. Again the value of R and C can be estimated from the following equation:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{RC} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where ω is the frequency that needs to be eliminated. For elimination of 314.16 rad/sec (or 50 Hz) we used $R = 9.645 \text{ K}\Omega$ and $C = 0.22 \text{ }\mu\text{F}$.

B.4 Inverting Amplifier

Figure B.4: Circuit diagram of an inverting amplifier

Two identical inverting amplifiers have been used in the circuit to amplify the weak signal, coming from the strain gauge. In general for arbitrary resistances $R1$ and $R2$, the gain in voltage can be determined from the following expression.

$$\text{Gain (G)} = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = -\frac{R_2}{R_1}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

In each amplifier of our circuit, the value of R_1 was $20\text{ K}\Omega$ and R_2 was $100\text{ K}\Omega$. The net gain achieved was 25.

Appendix C

Details of chapter 4

Graphical representation of Hankel function of second kind

Figure C.1: Figures showing the real and imaginary parts of Hankel function of second kind

Figure C.2: Schematic of infinite plate oscillating in air with velocity v

Oscillation of infinite plate in a viscous medium

For the plate oscillating in x-direction, the governing equation can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

These notations should not be confused with the previous one. Here:

u = velocity of the medium,

ν = kinematic viscosity of the medium.

Let the velocity of the plate be written as:

$$v = v_0 e^{i\omega t}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

The steady state solution of the equation (C.1) is of the form $u = U(y)e^{i\omega t}$. Substituting $u = U(y)e^{i\omega t}$ in equation (C.1) we obtain,

$$i\omega U(y) = \nu \frac{d^2 U(y)}{dy^2}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Solving equation (C.3), and considering the decaying solution we obtain:

$$u(y, t) = v_0 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\nu}}(1+i)y + i\omega t} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

or

$$u(y, t) = v_0 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\nu}}y + i\omega t} \left(\cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\nu}}y\right) - i \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\nu}}y\right) \right). \quad (\text{C.5})$$

Here the term $\sqrt{\frac{2\nu}{\omega}}$ represents the depth through which the viscous disturbance propagates into the medium. For the present case the value was found to be 0.000257 m. As mentioned earlier since this value was much smaller than the diameter of the oscillating cylinder of our problem, we used the solution obtained in equation (C.5) to estimate the viscous losses due to the oscillating cylinder.

Bibliography

- [1] H.L. Caswell. Investigation of low temperature internal friction. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 29(8):1210–1214, 1958.
- [2] D.D.L. Chung. Review materials for vibration damping. *Journal of Materials Science*, 36(24):5733–5737, 2001.
- [3] G.E. Dieter and D.J. Bacon. *Mechanical Metallurgy*. McGraw-Hill Series in Materials Science and Engineering. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 1988.
- [4] J.D. Eshelby. Dislocations as a cause of mechanical damping in metals. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 197(1050):396–416, 1949.
- [5] L.B. Felsen and N. Marcuvitz. *Radiation and Scattering of Waves*. IEEE Press Series on Electromagnetic Wave Theory. Wiley, 1994.
- [6] J.A. Salem and G.D. Quinn. Effect of lateral cracks on fracture toughness determined by the surface-crack-in-flexure method. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 85(4):873–880, 2002.
- [7] P. Jana and A. Chatterjee. An internal damping formula derived from dispersed elasto-plastic flaws with weibull-distributed strengths. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 87(0):137–149, 2014.

-
- [8] R.A. Khan, L. Singh and M.L. Aggarwal. Relationship between damping factor and compressive residual stress for shot-peened austenitic stainless steel. *International Scholarly Research Network*, 2011(867484), 2011.
- [9] L. Meirovitch. *Fundamentals of Vibrations*. McGraw-Hill higher education. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 2002.
- [10] M.P. Nascimento, R.C. Souza, W.L. Pigatin and H.J.C. Voorwald. Effects of surface treatments on the fatigue strength of aisi 4340 aeronautical steel. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 23(7):607–618, 2001.
- [11] S.S. Singh, P.K. Rohatgi, D. Nath and B.N. Keshavaram. Factors affecting the damping capacity of cast aluminium-matrix composites. *Journal of Materials Science*, 29(22):5975–5984, 1994.
- [12] D.D.L. Chung and S. Wen. Enhancing the vibration reduction ability of concrete by using steel reinforcement and steel surface treatments. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 30(2):327–330, 2000.
- [13] W. De Silva Clarence. *Vibration Damping, Control, and Design*. Taylor & Francis, 2007.
- [14] J. Wilks. Dislocation damping in metals. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 16(5):587, 1965.